

**THE EXPERIENCE OF OTHER COUNTRIES IN THE TRAINING OF MODERN
MANAGERS IN THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM****Temirov Artik Suyunovich**

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Abstract. *This article examines the specifics of the professional training of modern managers in France. The author focuses on innovative teaching methods based on globalization and the integration of strategic thinking. The main emphasis is on the role of Higher Commercial Schools, which provide students with both theoretical knowledge and practical skills. The importance of international cooperation and the introduction of advanced educational technologies to improve the professionalism of future leaders is emphasized. The article also provides examples of successful graduates who have taken high positions in the private sector of the economy. Today, the modern intellectual landscape of the world is changing dramatically, and technology and industry are entering the process of rapid development. It's no secret that in such a situation, the quality and efficiency of the education provided to the younger generation lag behind the level of general development. There are international integration processes in the field of education. it is impossible to achieve something important without leaving the local borders. Rapid development creates many problems that make people think. For example, the problem of improving the quality of education creates obstacles even for large countries of the world, special attention to the organization of conditions and work by qualified personnel and employers always leads to an increase in the efficiency of the organization.*

Keywords: *Professional Education, Leadership Training, France, Globalization, Strategic Thinking, Modern Management.*

**ОПЫТ ДРУГИХ СТРАН В ПОДГОТОВКЕ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ МЕНЕДЖЕРОВ В
СИСТЕМЕ ВЫСШЕГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ**

Аннотация. *Во этой статье рассматриваются особенности профессиональной подготовки современных руководителей во Франции. Автор акцентирует внимание на инновационных методах обучения, основанных на глобализации и интеграции стратегического мышления. Основной упор делается на роль Высших коммерческих школ, которые обеспечивают студентов как теоретическими знаниями, так и практическими навыками. Подчёркивается важность международного сотрудничества и внедрения передовых образовательных технологий для повышения профессионализма будущих*

лидеров. В статье также приводятся примеры успешных выпускников, занявших высокие должности в частном секторе экономики.

Ключевые слова: *Профессиональное образование, Подготовка лидеров, Франция, Глобализация, Стратегическое мышление, Современный менеджмент.*

The emergence of modern trends in the process of economic and social development undoubtedly leads to an increase in the need for modern leaders. Taking into account that the proper establishment of the higher education system is of particular importance in the development of our country, it becomes clear how important the need for long-term and consistent reforms is.

Currently, serious steps are being taken to develop the higher education system in our country. The amount of funds for the development of education is increasing every year, and this serves to form new approaches. We are increasingly witnessing the effective use of foreign best practices in the training of highly qualified, modern leaders. At the same time, in the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 "On measures for the further development of the higher education system" No. striving for wide implementation of technologies, active involvement in educational and methodological activities based on educational programs and educational materials, conducting master classes, friendly foreign education "training courses for highly qualified teachers and scientists of the institutions, systematically organizing internships for young teachers and researchers, as well as retraining and upgrading the qualifications of professors and teachers" have been defined.

To date, as a result of reforms in the context of higher education, educational programs have been developed, high-level training of specialists necessary for modern and future production, creation of a logical structure and determination of the exact sequence of learning academic subjects, introduction of an interdisciplinary approach to the organization of the educational process, audience important measures are also being implemented in the matter of study time between classes and independent work, individualization of training. The study and analysis of educational programs allow us to conclude that the training of specialists in economics and management at HEIs is based on a solid theoretical foundation. This determines the wide use of personnel in research and teaching activities in the higher education system.

The Graduate School of Business in Paris not only provides employment to its graduates, but also opens the way to the highest positions. At the same time, it should be noted that school graduates consider internships at universities in the US and Canada to be the most effective way to supplement their knowledge. Every fourth out of ten graduates of the Higher Business School

will hold senior management positions in the private sector of the economy, and the percentage of those employed in the manufacturing sector will reach 90%.

In France, when hiring managers of enterprises and institutions, they prefer graduates of higher commercial schools over universities. Since the education in many universities is both theoretical and practical in production, university graduates are often given a responsible job in industry without an 'apprenticeship' period. When comparing the training of specialists in the field of management carried out in universities and higher commercial schools, it was found that the superiority of university training has a solid theoretical basis based on general universal knowledge and predetermines the wide use of graduates in research and teaching activities in the higher education system.

The lack of narrow specialization, professionalization of teaching, limited practice in enterprises, and organizations, and as a result, insufficient skills and practical management skills formed in the field of organizational management do not allow university graduates to immediately occupy leadership positions. Most of them need to get professional diplomas to get a good job and promotion.

Close cooperation of higher education institutions with industrial enterprises is the best way to apply research results and involve them in the economic process, which allows to creation new products, technologies, and services. It also contributes to the development of the economy and the social sphere and, accordingly, provides the opportunity to support structural changes in the areas where the universities are located.

In order to solve the modern tasks of training leaders due to the rapid development of information and communication technologies, the general computerization and robotization of production, changes in the structures and priorities of organizations, the management and teachers of modern vocational higher schools in France modernize the content and technology of personnel training, the specific features of the educational system, they take the experience of foreign management schools and adapt it to themselves.

According to the current practice, the educational process in higher schools is traditionally divided into several areas: acquisition of certain practical skills and abilities; get information; development of strategic thinking skills. However, the assumption that the thought process exists separately from actual actions and is not aimed at acquiring additional knowledge seems incomplete. The only way to improve the quality of teaching is to develop technologies that allow you to activate, stimulate and control the thinking process.

The features of professional training of modern leaders in higher education are as follows:

1) The modularity of knowledge formation, which opens up the possibility of correcting or replacing modules depending on the importance of changes in the subject area, the environment, or even a change in specialization.

2) Multi-functionality of graduate training, partial exchange of knowledge modules, their redundancy.

3) The high technological efficiency of the organization of the educational process is achieved through the use of a complex of active technologies aimed at the development of today's international and future leader and the formation of his professional and personal qualities in the educational process.

Thus, the idea of globalization is based on the process of forming a single international community, which is the international educational community, the comprehensive convergence of peoples and countries. This rule is based on the rapid development of scientific and technical progress, the development of educational technologies and information communications.

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